

A METHOD FOR BETTER UNDERSTANDING OF NATIVE LANGUAGE LECTURE TEXTS FOR STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8058563>

Abstract: This article talks about what to pay attention to when understanding lecture activities in teaching the mother tongue.

Key words: Start reading a text immediately, understand a sentence, write words, read aloud from a dictionary, translate a text, interpret words and sentences from texts

I recommend the following method for understanding native language lectures:

1. Start reading the text at once. This is the best method and it will be very useful for the students.
2. Try to understand a single part of the text or a sentence. It will help you to read the sentence again.
3. Write the words and read them clearly from the dictionary. It is very important to familiarize yourself with the words used in the lecture.
4. Avoid misunderstanding the main concepts of the text. This approach itself is not very easy, so you need to understand this process with a thumbs up.
5. Try to translate the text. Theoretical concepts in the text are thought through translation.
6. Try to answer the questions in the text. Compare the text of the lecture to organize it and find answers to the questions to identify gaps.
7. Read the lecture again. It helps to understand if we read and listen several times.
8. Include the lecture in your speech. It helps to rest frequently used words and phrases from the lecture text.

The following methods are useful for better understanding of native language lecture texts:

1. Interpreting words and sentences from texts: Study analysis to gather information about words and sentences that appear in a text and understand how they have changed.
2. Marking: Understanding can be enhanced by extracting marks from the text according to the following purposes: the most important ideas, recommended actions in aviation, etc.
3. Read parts of the text more continuously: Read the text directly or a part and then read another part. This method increases comprehension to confirm the target to be copied in the native language.
4. Use of audio and video materials: If the lecture is in audio or video format, use it. It is also possible to increase understanding with the help of events and activities that add additional information to the text.
5. Collection of lecture texts and test questions: Increase understanding of the native language by analyzing questions or testing students. This method is useful for memorization and practical training.

With these methods, it is easy to understand native language lectures.

References:

1. State educational standard and curriculum of general secondary education. Mother tongue. Literature. Uzbek language (for schools where education is conducted in other languages). Tashkent. "Sharq" publishing-printing concern.
2. "Law on Education" of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
September 23, 2020
3. Karima Kasimova, Safo Matchonov, Khalida Gulomova, Sharofat Yoldosheva, Sharoljon Sariyev "Methodology of mother tongue teaching" Tashkent "Nasir" publishing house. 2009
4. A. Gulomov, M. Kadirov, M. Ernazarova, et al. Methodology of mother tongue teaching. - T.: "Science and technology", 2012

